

A NEW PROCESS FOR QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATION OF ANTIMONY AND ITS SEPARATION FROM TIN AND LEAD BY MEANS OF ALKALI SULPHOCYANIDES.

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Antimony reacts with the alkali sulphocyanides in a moderately strong and boiling hydrochloric acid solution with the formation of antimony trisulphide. Tin and lead, if present, remain in solution. Nitric acid and nitrates must be absent and sulphuric acid gives high result even in the absence of lead due to separation of sulphur.

If to a cold hydrochloric acid solution of antimony, alkali sulphocyanides are added, the solution remains clear, no precipitate comes down. But if the solution is made to boil, a turbidity appears which gradually passes from orange-red to scarlet-red precipitate of the antimony compound. The reaction possibly occurs according to the following equations:—

Evolution of H_2S gas during the reaction indicates a partial decomposition of the sulphide by the hydrochloric acid present. Hence the solution should be diluted for complete precipitation.

Procedure.—Samples containing about 0.1 g. of antimony was weighed out in a 600 c.c. beaker and sufficient nitric acid (*d 1.2*) added to decompose the substance completely, followed by a few c.c. of HCl to dissolve the oxides formed. The solution was brought to a syrupy consistency by evaporating on a water-bath. HCl (20 c.c.) was again added and the solution evaporated to a small bulk. This process is repeated until the whole of HNO_3 was completely removed. The solution was made up to 125 to 150 c.c. containing 20 to 25 c.c. free hydrochloric acid. It was allowed to boil freely on the hot plate. A saturated solution of ammonium thiocyanate (25-30 c.c.) was then added to this boiling solution. A pink coloration appeared for a moment and red precipitate of Sb_2S_3 separated out. After a minute it was removed from the hot plate and allowed to settle for five minutes. The volume was then diluted upto 300 c.c. for complete precipitation of the sulphide. The precipitate was then quickly filtered through a weighed Gooch crucible, washed first with hydrogen sulphide water, then with

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hot water to remove the chloride and sulphocyanide. Carbon disulphide washing followed next and it removed any free sulphur (if present) at this stage. Lastly, the precipitate was washed with alcohol and heated for two hours in a drying oven at 200° to 300°.

Fairly good results are obtained (when too much of tin or lead is present) by reprecipitating the sulphide with thiocyanate from acid (HCl) solution as described above. The weight of the precipitate multiplied by 71.42 gives the percentage of antimony.

Weight taken.	Sb ₂ S ₃		Weight taken.	Sb ₂ S ₃	
	Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
Tartar emetic (0.4158 g.) + tin (0.5010 g.) + lead (0.20 g.)	0.2100 g.	0.2104 g.	Tartar emetic (0.4108 g.) + tin (0.1210 g.) + Pb- (NO ₃) ₂ (0.1010 g.)	0.1511 g.	0.1524 g.
Tartar emetic (0.4003 g.) + tin (0.4120) + lead (0.202 g.)	0.2019	0.2025	Tartar emetic (0.3606 g.) + tin (0.2008 g.) + Pb(NO ₃) ₂ (0.0998 g.)	0.1329	0.1340
Tartar emetic (0.3234 g.) + tin (0.10 g.) + Pb(NO ₃) ₂ (0.015 g.)	0.1190	0.1202	Tartar emetic (0.1020 g.) + tin (0.1985 g.) + Pb- (NO ₃) ₂ (0.2088 g.)	0.0369	0.0379
Tartar emetic (0.1520 g.) + tin (0.0980 g.) + Pb(NO ₃) ₂ (0.2108 g.)	0.0538	0.0602			

It is better to keep tin in the higher state of oxidation, *i.e.*, in the stannic form before the sulphocyanides are added. Stannous tin has a tendency to fall down with antimony as sulphide. The behaviour of lead is somewhat different in this case. Lead remains in solution under the conditions of the experiment and is not precipitated either as chloride or sulphide.

